

Pedagogical Principles in the Development of Independent Education and Educational Tasks of Students

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Annotation:

The article deals with the issue of independent education development in higher education institutions, in particular, the improvement of educational tasks, analytical study of their content, independent works revealing the essence of the subject, and the creation of scientific and methodological bases for the development of educational tasks. important recommendations and conclusions regarding the review of the criteria for evaluating students' knowledge are presented.

Keywords: independent education, educational content, cognitive tasks, practical activities, educational tasks, question, task, evaluation criteria, knowledge, skills and competencies.

In training future specialists and improving the quality of the educational process, independent work that allows students to engage in creative activities and develop their intellectual abilities has a special place.

A student's independent work is a work on a certain list of topics allocated for independent education, provided with educational and methodological literature and recommendations, controlled in the form of tests, exams, colloquiums, abstracts and lectures. understood. Currently, there are different approaches to the methodology of organizing students' independent work. Some researchers consider independent work as students' perception and independent understanding of information given by teachers. Others reveal the essence of this phenomenon only with external signs. Others define independent work by such criteria as independent acquisition and in-depth understanding of new knowledge, measuring the amount of time students spend independently and studying the set questions. It follows that independent work is not only a form, but also a learning tool, because it develops certain skills and abilities of students, performing a number of functions.

In recent years, a number of scientific-methodological studies on the methodology of mother tongue teaching have been conducted in our country. Including Sh. Yusupova¹ and N.Yuldasheva² etc., in their research, advocated the teaching of the mother tongue based on new pedagogical technologies. A.G'ulomov³, M.Saidov⁴ and N.Alavuddinovas⁵ conducted research on the methodology of independent work and creative thinking skills formation through mother tongue teaching. Also, a number of studies were conducted on the methodology of teaching language levels from the mother tongue in continuous education, including T. Yusupova conducted scientific research on the methodology of teaching the main parts of the sentence.⁶ The content of this article can be widely used in state language education today.

The developmental function increases intellectual work culture, introduces students to creative activities, and enriches the student's intellectual abilities. Information and teaching includes the educational activities of students in classrooms. Guidance and encouragement give the educational process the character of professional orientation. The purpose of the educational function is to form and develop the professional qualities of the future specialist. The research function forms a new level of professional and creative thinking.

The following are distinguished as signs of independent work: the presence of a cognitive or practical task, a problematic issue; task completion time; manifestation of mental stress; consciousness, independence and activity of students in the process of solving assigned problems; to manage the student's independent, cognitive and practical activities. Thus, the true essence of independent work is a cognitive or problematic task that determines the entire educational process.

Independent work has an activity-based nature, and therefore it is possible to determine the components specific to the activity: motivational relationships, defining a specific task, choosing methods of implementation, making connections, and controlling. The following conditions must be met for effective independent work:

- to encourage the educational task;
- clear formation of cognitive tasks;
- algorithm, method of work execution, student's knowledge of its execution;
- clearly defining the report forms, scope of work, deadlines for its submission by the teacher;
- determination of types of consulting assistance (thematic, problematic advice);
- evaluation criteria, reporting, etc.;
- types and forms of control (seminar, test, test, seminar, etc.).

1 Yusupova Sh. Ona tili ta'limi samaradorligini oshirish va ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalarni joriy etish: ped. fan. nom-di diss. TDPI. –T.,1998.– 137 b.

2 Yuldasheva N. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida lug'aviy sinonimlarni yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida o'qitish metodikasi: ped.fan. nomzodi ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilan diss.–T., 2002. –123b.

3 Gulyamov A. Metodika razvitiya uchebno - poznovatelnoy aktivnosti uchastixsya v protsesse prepodovaniya rodnogo (uzbekskogo) yazyka: Dis. dok. ped. nauk. –T.: TGPI, 1991. – 37 b.

4 Saidov M. O'zbek maktablarining 5-sinflarida ona tili ta'limi jarayonida tafakkurni rivojlantiruvchi o'quv topshiriqlari va ulardan foydalanish metodikasi: ped. fan. nom-di diss. avtoref.TDPU. –Toshkent, 2000.– 25 b.

5 Alavuddinova N. Ona tili darslarida ijodiy fikrlash ko'nikmasini shakllantirish metodikasi: ped. fan. nom-di diss. avtoref.TDPU. – T., 2008.– 24 b.

6 Yusupova T. Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi asosida maktabda o'quvchilarga bosh bo'laklarni o'rgatish: ped. fan. nom-di diss. avtoref.TDPI. –T.,1998.– 22 b.

Independent work includes reproduction and creative processes in the student's activity. Depending on this, three levels of independent work are distinguished.

The reproductive level includes reading, recording educational literature, listening to lectures, audio and video recordings, memorizing, retelling, memorizing, Internet resources, repeating educational material. Cognitive research includes preparing messages, lectures, speeches, writing abstracts, essays, tests, preparation for business games, etc. The creative level - the level of independent work - includes writing scientific articles, theses, participation in research work, participation in student scientific conferences, Olympiads, etc. In order to organize and successfully implement independent work of students, the proportion of independent work at all levels is necessary. According to the level of difficulty, there are four types of student independent work.

The first type develops the ability to perform tasks according to the model. The latter helps to reproduce information from memory. The third is aimed at learning how to solve atypical problems. The fourth involves performing tasks aimed at creative activity. A prerequisite for successful independent work is a combination of all the above types and levels of work. When organizing students' independent work, it is necessary to take into account different levels of preparation of students and different methods of educational activity. When choosing tasks, the teacher should follow the following criteria.

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